

After Constantine

Issue 3
(June 2023)

AC

STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

Orthodox Academy of Crete

AFTER CONSTANTINE
STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND
EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

ISSN 2732-8260

After Constantine issue 3 (June 2023)

Published by the Orthodox Academy of Crete (www.oac.gr)

All papers copyright are held by the authors and became available by the Creative Commons Attribution License

CC-BY creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0

Editorial Board

Andreas Kuelzer (Austrian Academy of Sciences)
Vanya Lozanova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences)
Panagiotis Manafis (University of Patras)
Efi Ragia (University of Thessaly)
Zoe Tsiami (University of Thessaly)
Sercan Yandim Aydin (Hacettepe University)
Yannis Varalis (University of Thessaly)
Luca Zavagno (Bilkent University)
Constantine Zorbas (Director of Orthodox Academy of Crete)

Editors

Zoe Tsiami
Philippos Vlahoulis (University of Thessaly)

Graphic sketch

Byzantine tales - History in comics
Find out more at: byzantinetales.com

Chrysa Sakel
Spyros Theocharis

Table of Contents

Coptic Letters from the Brooklyn Museum

Sohair Ahmed p. 1

Easter recycling. Thanatological Motifs in the texts of the
Christians of the North

Nadiezhda Gayevskaya p. 8

The Metaphors of Motion in Athanasius' Account of
Idolatry

Viacheslav V. Lytvynenko p. 22

Book Review

Zeuxippos or Byzantion: The City of the Sun.

Valeria Fol p. 35

AC

STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

AC

Constantine the Great by *Chrzyśa Sakel*

COPTIC LETTERS FROM THE BROOKLYN MUSEUM

Sohair Ahmed*

This paper presents publishing five Coptic *ostraca*, one is a limestone chip and the others are potsherds. These *ostraca* represent uncompleted letters including a request which is missed partly or completely in the texts here. There is a suggestion of reading and translating the texts made by Professor Wintermute a long time ago, but he didn't publish them and agreed to be published by me. The museum sent me permission to publish in 2019 and I took photos of the *ostraca* in 2022.

Keywords: Coptic, Letter, *Ostraca*, Request.

The Coptic letters were official, ecclesiastical, personal, or practical.[1] Their topics are request, order, instructions, blaming, complaint, information, or just greeting. The texts here represent letters including a request (not complete in texts).

The Coptic letters of request are numerous and contain either asking for a loan, favor, meeting, visit, prayer, advice, payment, division(something),[2] or settlement (between two persons).[3] The favor asked in these letters was often sending or bringing something (like money)[4] or someone, with or without fees (e.g. asking for bringing someone as a servant for a sick woman).[5]

Signs for publishing used in this case:

[ⲁⲃⲚ] Letters missing from the original text due to lacuna, restored by the editor.

ⲁ(ⲃⲚ) Abbreviation /symbol in the text, expanded by the editor.

ⲁⲃ Ⲛ Letters not clear entirely in the text.

Ostracon 1

Potsherd X2004.148

Collection: Egyptian, Classical, Ancient Near Eastern Art

Object Number: 16.580.460

Culture: Unknown Egyptian artist

Title: Coptic Ostracon

Date: 332 B.C.E.-642 C.E.

Period: Ptolemaic Period to Late Antique Period

Geography: Place made: Egypt

Medium: Limestone, pigment

Dimensions: 4 15/16 x 3 9/16 x 11/16 in. (12.5 x 9 x 1.7 cm)

Description: From X2003 Egyptian, Classical, Ancient Middle Eastern Art

Conservation Survey Form, 1/4/00: Condition: Good

Content by me: Beginning of a letter, the sender addressed the letter to his mother and his brothers, it included a request, but it is erased completely.

Ostracon 1

1. ⲁⲛ[ⲟ]ϣ ⲙⲏ[ⲛⲁ]
2. ⲉⲓⲩⲓⲛⲉ ⲉⲧ[ⲁ]
3. ⲙⲁⲁϣ ⲙ[ⲛ ⲛ-]
4. ⲁϣⲛⲏϣ ⲧⲏ[ⲣⲟϣ]
5. ⲉⲛⲟϥⲓⲣⲏⲏ[ⲓ]
6. ⲁⲣⲓ ⲧ(ⲁⲓⲁⲛ)ⲏ ⲛ[ⲓ]
- 7.....

1. I am Me[na?]
2. I greet m[y]
3. Mother a[nd]
4. A[ll] my brothers
5. In a pea[ce]
6. Do charity a[nd]
7.[6]

1.1 The name of the sender starts with the letter ⲙ and according to the space of missed letters here, I suggest it to be “Mena” which is a familiar Christian name relating to Saint Mena who was depicted on flasks of water (used for healing) in Byzantine Egypt.[7]

1.5 ⲓⲣⲏⲛⲉ, ⲓⲣⲏⲏⲏ: A Greek loan word means “peace” mentioned in these forms in Sahidic and Fayyumic dialects.[8]

1.6 ⲁⲣⲓ ⲧⲏ: I suggest it as an uncommon abbreviation (Nomina Sacra) for ⲁⲣⲓ ⲧⲁⲓⲁⲛ “do charity” which is a polite formula written before requests in letters, abbreviate to ⲧⲁⲛⲏ or ⲧⲁⲓⲏ (the Coptic equivalent is ⲁⲣⲓ ⲛⲏⲁ “do favor”[9] and replaced sometimes by ⲁⲣⲓ ⲧⲏⲏⲧⲟⲛ “do brotherhood”.[10]

Ostrakon 2

Potsherd X2004.185

Collection: Egyptian, Classical, Ancient Near Eastern Art

ObjectNumber: 16.580.468

Culture: Unknown Egyptian artist

Title: Coptic Ostrakon

Date: late 2nd century B.C.

Geography: Place made: Thebes Egypt

Medium: Terracotta, pigment

Dimensions: 1 9/16 x 3/8 x 1 13/16 in. (4 x 1 x 4.6 cm)

Description: Receipt of two taxes paid at the bank of Diospolis (Thebes)

Content by me: It seems to be an official letter inscribed on both sides (not tax receipt), the sender was a scribe (or steward) and he writes to a man who seems to be headman, and part of his name is broken (because of a lacuna), the sender asked sending something missed also in the text (on the back) to be delivered by the man who brings this letter.

Ostrakon 2
(Recto)

Ostrakon 2
(Verso)

Ostrakon 4

Geography: Place made: Egypt

Medium: Terracotta, pigment

Dimensions: 1 15/16 x 5/16 x 2 7/16 in. (5 x 0.8 x 6.2 cm)

1 15/16 x 1/4 x 2 1/2 in. (4.9 x 0.7 x 6.3 cm)

Provenance: Ancient provenance not known; modern provenance not recorded, but the object has been in the Museum for many decades.

Historical Attributions: Unpublished book 11, Wintermute's Notes: no number E,p.14-15

Published References: Permission to publish granted to Dr. Sohair Ahmed – YB 6/2019

Content by me: A letter from John to Apa Moses (monks) mentions a person builds something missing in the text, then the sender asked the recipient a favor that giving this builder something (perhaps a tool or wage), which will be sent to the recipient by the master builder.

- 1.†ϣINE €[TEKMITCON]
- 2.[€T]NANOYC EIC[ZHTE?]]
- 3.[...]Χα κωτ[.....]
- 4.αρι πνα ντ[....]
- 5.[πχοεις] εφασμοϥ €ρ[οκ]
- 6.εις τκτϑν [NN]
- 7.[εφνατη]νοοϥ νακ μη [οοτϥ?]
- 8.[n...]ολε ταα[с] m
- 9.απα μωϥη[с]
10. ριτη ιωρα[nhс]

Ostrakon 5

Potsherd X2004-283

Collection: Egyptian, Classical, Ancient Near Eastern Art

ObjectNumber: 16.580.502

Culture: Unknown Demotic artist

Title: Coptic Ostrakon

Date: 332 B.C.E.-642 C.E.

Period: Ptolemaic Period to Late Antique Period

Geography: Place made: Egypt

Medium: Terracotta, pigment

Dimensions: 2 5/8 x 7/16 x 4 3/8 in. (6.7 x 1.1 x 11.1 cm)

Content by me: A part from letter mentioned a number of fruits and dry measure perhaps for sending, buying, selling, or paying them.

Ostrakon 5

11. πεκσον νε

12. λαϥϥ .

- 1.I greet [your] good[17][brotherhood]
- 2.Behold!
- 3.[NN] builds [something]
- 4.Do favor and [give him...[18]]
- 5.[May Lord] bless [you]
- 6.Look,(the) master builder [NN?]
- 7.[he will se-]nd it to you [by?][19]
- 8.[...]ole, give [it] to
- 9.Apa Moses
10. From John

11. Your brother the
12. humble

1.3 perhaps a proper name ends with $\chi\lambda$ (compare $\kappa\omicron\chi\lambda$).[20]

1.6 $\tau\bar{\kappa}\tau\bar{\omicron}\bar{\nu}$ from Greek origin refers to “master builder, architect”.[21]

1.8 [...]ολε I think it is as proper name, there are many Coptic personal names ended with ole, such as Paole, Peloole, and Stole.[22]

1.

+2. $\chi\epsilon\ \kappa\eta\lambda\beta\omega\kappa[\epsilon\dots]$

3. $\mu[\mu\lambda]\lambda\beta\ \eta\kappa\omicron\chi\kappa\ [\bar{\nu}\dots]$

4. $\sigma\eta\lambda\gamma\ \mu\mu\lambda\lambda\beta\ [\bar{\nu}\dots]$

5. $\omega[\dots]\ \mu\lambda\chi\epsilon[\]$

6-9.....traces.....

1.

+2. Because you will go[to (a place name/ a monastery name)]

3. The thirty of doum-fruits [to NN?]

4. Thirty two [of (fruits /measure)]

5. [three? of] Matia[of...]

6-9.traces.....

1.2 $\kappa\omicron\chi\kappa$ means fruit/nut of the doum palm. The ancient Egyptians made bread from it, mentioned in Coptic also as a proper name.[23] This word means also in Coptic “safflower” but I translate it as doum because there is no measure written after the number here, so it is a countable thing as “doum”.

1.4 $\mu\lambda\chi\epsilon$ or $\mu\lambda\lambda\chi\epsilon$ (rarely as $\mu\lambda\lambda\tau\epsilon$ or $\mu\lambda\tau\iota$) is a dry measure for grain, seeds, salt, and fruits, known from ancient Egypt as *medja*, and in Latin as *mation* (pl. as *matia*), its capacity is 12 to one artaba.[24]

Conclusions

-The request in letters nos.1 and 3 are now completely missed, while in the other letters here a part of the request is still appearing like giving

(something) to the letter carrier (no.2) or giving (something) to a builder on behalf of the master builder (no.4), and the last letter here mentioned doum fruits and a dry measure –which will be probably paid or sent to someone (no.5).

- The polite formula before the request is: do charity (nos. 1, 3) and do a favor (no.4).

-Using the invocation “May Lord bless you” after requesting a favor (no.4) and it is written usually after the greeting formula in Coptic correspondences.

-The verb used for the greeting formula here is “ $\omega\iota\eta\epsilon$ ” to express the simple greeting formula (nos.1-4).

- The woman called Mourgiria (no.3) was not the sender of the letter but she may be the wife, daughter or sister of the sender.

- The titles *prostates* and *tekton* (from Greek origin), they are not familiar in the Coptic letters (nos.2,4 here).

- The texts here can be dated from the 6th –the 8th centuries CE (according to the dating of the Coptic ostraca).

Notes

*Egyptian Assistant Professor in Coptic language, Faculty of Archaeology, in Shams University, Cairo-Egypt, published many Coptic documentary texts written on ostraca and papyri, prepared dictionaries about Professions and Titles, Arabic Terms, and Food and Drink in Coptic. Winner of the papyrology fellowship award from the USA in 2021(<https://classicalstudies.org/awards-and-fellowships/ludwig-koenen-fellowship>).

[1] Ahmed 2020, p.7.

[2] Ahmed 2008, no.6.

[3] Ibid. 2008, p.2.

[4] Ahmed 2022, no.1.

[5] Ahmed 2009, no.1.

[6] The request is erased entirely from here.

[7] Ahmed 2020, no. 4, p. 48.

- [8] Coptic Dictionary.org [last access 10/11/2022].
- [9] Förster 2007, WB, 3-5.
- [10] Ahmed 2009, no.1.
- [11] For more information, see: Crum 1939, 383b-384a & Ahmed 2011, p.196.
- [12] Ahmed 2022, no.1.
- [13] Förster 2007, WB, 693; Cherix 2016-2019, 165 b; Ahmed 2010, p.139.
- [14] For examples: Crum 1939, ST no. 337; Hasitzka 2007, nos. 151,161; P. Kellis 1, no.25; Crum 1902, no.68 and Ahmed 2022, no.1.
- [15] Wintermute didn't consider it as proper name and translated it as "bundle of bandages".
- [16] Hasitzka 2007, p.60b,61a.
- [17] Written in the next line.
- [18] Perhaps a tool for building or wage?
- [19] Another weak suggestion by me as: ⲙⲚⲏⲉⲗⲟⲟⲗⲉ "with the grapes", perhaps as wage.
- [20] Hasitzka 2007, p. 52b.
- [21] Förster 2007, WB, 799, Cherix 2016-2019, 174b.
- [22] Hasitzka 2007, p. 70a; Cherix 2016-2019, 75a, 95b.
- [23] Crum 1939 100b; Cherix 2016-2019, 16b; Ahmed 2020-21, 26,5.
- [24] Alcock 1996, p.3; Crum 1939, 213a.

Bibliography

1. Ahmed, S. (2008). *A Group of Unpublished Coptic Ostraca from the Cairo Museum, Vol. 1*. Cairo: al-Zaïm publishing house.
2. Ahmed, S. (2009). Four Coptic Ostraca from Kharga Museum. *BAPCI* (26), pp. 163-187.
3. Ahmed, S. (2010 & 2011). Professions, Trades, Occupations and Titles in Coptic –Alphabetically I, II. *J CoptS* (12&13) [online], pp. 115-148, pp. 183-212. Available at: <https://shams.academia.edu/SohairAhmed> and <https://coptica.ch/indices> [Last access 12 November 2022]
4. Ahmed, S. (2020). Eleven Coptic Papyri from Beinecke Library- Yale University with Glossary of Currency in Coptic. *BACS* [Online] (1). Available at: <https://shams.academia.edu/SohairAhmed> [Last access 12 November 2022].
5. Ahmed, S. (2020-2021). Food and Drink in Coptic Texts- an Alphabetical List, *BACS* [Online] (2). Available at: <https://shams.academia.edu/SohairAhmed> and <https://coptica.ch/indices> [Last access 12 November 2022].
6. Ahmed, S. (2022). Coptic Ostraca Mentioning Money. *After Constantine: Stories from the Late Antique and Early Byzantine Era* [online] (2), pp. 1-22. Available at www.afterconstantine.com/issues [Last access 12 November 2022].
7. Alcock, A. (1996). Coptic Terms for Containers and Measures. *Enchoria* (23), pp. 1-7.
8. Cherix, P. (2016-2019). *Lexique Copte-dialects ahidique, PDF, V .19.1* [Online]. Available at: <https://coptica.ch/indices> [Last Access 12 November 2022].
9. Crum, W. (1902). *Coptic Ostraca from the Collections of the Egypt Exploration Fund the Cairo Museum and Others*. London: The Egypt Exploration Fund.

10. Crum, W. (1921). *Short Texts from Coptic Ostraca and Papyri*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
11. Crum, W. (1939). *A Coptic Dictionary*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
12. Förster, H. (2002). *Wörterbuch der Griechischen Wörter inden Koptische Dokumentarischen Texten*. Berlin, New York.: Walter de Gruyter.
13. Gardner, I. et al. (1999). *Coptic Documentary Texts from Kellis, vol. 1*. Oxbow: Oxbow Books Limited.
14. Hasitzka, M. (2007). *Namen in Koptischen Dokumentarischen Texten*, [Online]. Available at: www.onb.ac.at & <https://coptica.ch/indices> [Last access 12 November 2022].
15. Stefanski, E., Lichtheim, M. (1952). *Coptic Ostraca from Medinet Habu*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Websites

1. *Coptic Dictionary Online*. Available at: Coptic-Dictionary.org [Last access 12 November 2022].
2. *Checklist of Editions Coptic Ostraca*. Available at <https://papyri.info/docs/checklist> [Last access 12 November 2022].

Partners & Collaborators

Medievalists.net

WHERE THE MIDDLE AGES BEGIN

**WORLD HISTORY
ENCYCLOPEDIA**

THE SECOND VOLUME OF
"BASIL BASILEUS"
FROM **BYZANTINE TALES**
IS OUT!

2. NOTHOS

ON PAPERBACK AND EBOOK IS AVAILABLE ON
AMAZON

NIS AND BYZANTIUM

THE COLLECTION OF SCIENTIFIC WORKS

Expand your knowledge
on Byzantium through
the podcast

BYZANTIO EXPLAINED

ISSN 2732-8260